

A CASE STUDY OF THE ACADEMIC STRUGGLES, COPING MECHANISMS, AND SUPPORT SYSTEMS OF A 16-YEAR-OLD FEMALE WITH READING DIFFICULTIES IN AN INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SETTING

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ABSTRACT

This case study explores the academic struggles, coping mechanisms, and support systems of a 16-year-old female student with reading difficulties within an inclusive education setting in a private school in the Philippines. Grounded in Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, and Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory, the study examines how teachers without specialized training address the learner's needs through social interaction, differentiated instruction, and motivational support. A single-case study design was employed, utilizing semi-structured interviews with the student, her mother, teachers, and a school administrator, complemented by structured classroom observations and document analysis. Thematic analysis was used to identify recurring patterns related to the student's challenges, coping strategies, and the effectiveness of instructional and institutional supports. Findings reveal significant foundational literacy deficits that hinder academic performance, alongside emergent coping mechanisms such as peer collaboration and reliance on visual aids. Teachers implemented differentiated strategies despite limited training, while systemic support under Republic Act No. 11650 was present but inconsistently applied. The study underscores the need for early identification, sustained teacher professional development, and strengthened implementation of inclusive education policies to better support learners with reading difficulties.

Keywords: *Reading Difficulties, Inclusive Education, Differentiated Instruction, Teacher Training, Republic Act No. 11650*

INTRODUCTION

Reading is a multifaceted cognitive process that evolves gradually from word recognition to comprehension through continuous practice and exposure (Kaya, 2015; Alexander, 2015). Beyond decoding words, comprehension requires the integration of prior knowledge, engagement, and effective reading strategies (Fisher, 2016). Furthermore, literacy development is not merely cognitive but also social, as Barton et al. (2016) noted that reading emerges through everyday interactions. Similarly, Antonio and Santillan (2020) emphasized that reading nurtures intellectual, emotional, and social growth, while McIntyre et al. (2017) underscored the role of early home literacy in shaping formal reading instruction.

Despite these insights, many learners continue to face barriers caused by specific disabilities leading to reading difficulties (Peterson & Pennington, 2015). Research by Dehaene et al. (2020) revealed that reading difficulties involve atypical brain activity in areas responsible for phonological processing. Consequently, reading difficulties can result in emotional distress and poor academic outcomes (De Clercq-Quaegebeur et al., 2018). Although studies show that early intervention can significantly improve reading skills (Livingston et al., 2018), the 2018 Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) results revealed that Filipino learners scored 150 points below the global average in reading (San Juan, 2019), highlighting the need for improved identification and support systems.

Students experiencing reading difficulties often struggle to understand concepts across academic subjects, resulting in widespread underperformance. Rivera and Aggabao (2020) emphasized that weak foundational literacy negatively affects learning in multiple disciplines and contributes to long-term academic disengagement. Without early support, the compounding effects of reading difficulties can hinder not only classroom success but also future participation in work and civic life. Foorman and Al Otaiba et al. (2019) and Fletcher and Vaughn (2021) supported this by asserting that early intervention is critical in disrupting cycles of academic failure and promoting equitable learning outcomes.

Reading difficulties are also closely linked to broader social and economic disadvantages. According to Hancock et al. (2025), children who continue to struggle with reading face increased risks of school dropout, unemployment, and long-term dependency on social support systems. Endress et al. (2018) stressed that reading is not merely an academic task but a foundational life skill that influences all learning areas and social engagement. Eissa (2015) and Sanopao (2016) both noted that poor reading skills hinder students' ability to perform well across subjects, especially when these difficulties go undiagnosed. When students demonstrate limited progress despite effort, this may indicate the presence of learning conditions such as reading difficulties, which often remain unidentified. Early identification of reading difficulties is thus essential not only for academic achievement but also for emotional well-being and lifelong development.

Dolan's (2023) reflective account highlighted the emotional and academic impact of undiagnosed reading difficulties, such as frustration, ridicule, and reduced self-esteem. This aligns with the findings of the 2001 Task Force on Dyslexia, which reported that teachers often lacked awareness and strategies to support learners with such difficulties. Cariño and Bailey (2024) echoed this concern in the context of Filipino public schools, where many educators are underprepared to identify or support students with reading difficulties. Reading difficulties manifest beyond basic decoding challenges, affecting spelling, word recognition, and overall reading comprehension—challenges that become more severe in the absence of timely support (González-Pulido et al., 2025). Undiagnosed reading difficulties deprive learners of opportunities for meaningful progress and self-confidence, reinforcing the urgency of early diagnosis and appropriate intervention.

Extensive research confirms that early interventions are both practical and effective in addressing reading difficulties. Al Otaiba et al. (2019) and Connor et al. (2019) provided evidence that when students receive strong classroom instruction paired with individualized interventions, significant improvements in reading outcomes can be achieved. Foorman and Al Otaiba et al. (2019) estimated that high-quality teaching can reduce the percentage of struggling readers to 5%, while targeted interventions can lower that rate further to 1–3%. Fletcher and Vaughn (2021) emphasized that sustained results depend on school-wide systems such as early screening, data-driven instruction, and well-prepared educators. The National Center on Response to Intervention (2010) added that multi-tiered models, such as RTI (response to intervention), offer promising pathways for meeting diverse student needs—including those with reading difficulties.

Despite these insights, literacy performance in the Philippines continues to be alarmingly low. According to Librea et al. (2023), many Filipino students, particularly at the elementary level, show poor reading proficiency, a trend worsened by learning disruptions during the COVID-19 pandemic. UNICEF (2022) reported that only 15% of Filipino school-aged children can read simple texts, an alarming statistic that highlights the depth of the crisis. These issues are even more pressing for children with undiagnosed reading difficulties, who face compounding barriers to academic success. The Philippine government has responded through legislation such as Republic Act No. 11650, known as the Inclusive Education Act, which aims to provide equitable educational access for children with disabilities.

However, Allam and Martin (2021) pointed out that implementation remains inconsistent, particularly regarding SPED training and resources. As inclusion becomes more widely recognized, there is a growing need to build teacher capacity and foster positive teacher attitudes. According to Abrazado et al. (2021), inclusive education requires comprehensive teacher preparation. Rheinberg and Engeser (2018) stressed the importance of motivation, appropriate instructional strategies, and ongoing professional development. As UNESCO (2001) concluded, inclusive education benefits all learners by fostering empathy, diversity, and a sense of belonging in classrooms.

Underscoring the emotional and psychological dimensions of learning challenges, Carmichael et al. (2014) found that learning disabilities such as reading difficulties can

have long-term negative effects on students' mental health and sense of belonging. This is further supported by earlier studies from Sideridis et al. (2019), and O'Keefe and Harackiewicz (2017), who demonstrated how academic struggles—particularly in literacy—can erode motivation, increase anxiety, and impair emotional development.

Learners with reading difficulties develop a variety of coping strategies to navigate academic challenges. Guided by Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, these strategies often arise through social interaction and guided learning within the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). With the assistance of teachers and peers, students develop greater independence through scaffolding—a gradual withdrawal of support as competence improves (Vygotsky, 1978). This theoretical framework emphasizes the importance of collaborative and contextualized learning activities that help students bridge the gap between what they can do independently and what they can achieve with guidance.

In addition, Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (1983) provides another perspective for understanding how learners with reading difficulties cope with academic demands. Many rely on strengths in spatial, musical, or kinesthetic intelligences to compensate for challenges in reading and writing. By recognizing these diverse intelligences, educators can design flexible learning opportunities such as visual aids, rhythmic reading, and movement-based literacy tasks. These inclusive approaches allow learners to express comprehension through their individual strengths, thereby reducing anxiety and promoting self-confidence (Takahashi, 2013; Andreou et al., 2013).

Complementing these frameworks, Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (1985) highlights how intrinsic motivation—driven by autonomy, competence, and relatedness—enhances coping among learners with reading difficulties. When students feel empowered, capable, and supported, they are more likely to persevere through academic challenges. This underscores the importance of nurturing emotional well-being alongside cognitive growth (Rheinberg & Engeser, 2018).

However, research shows that institutional barriers often limit the effectiveness of these coping mechanisms. Hossain et al. (2021) found that many learners with reading difficulties perceive academic environments as inflexible and unsupportive, often relying more on peers than faculty for assistance. Mortimore (2013) reported that while some schools provide resources, many students still experience disinterest or lack of empathy from educators. Cameron (2024) further argued that rigid assessment systems fail to accommodate the unique needs of learners with reading difficulties, leading to frustration and disengagement.

Despite these obstacles, numerous studies reveal the resilience of learners with reading difficulties in developing compensatory strategies. Hossain et al. (2021) and Pirttimaa et al. (2015) noted that these students often use assistive technologies, restructure study routines, or employ visual and kinesthetic methods to enhance comprehension. Doikou-Avliadou (2015) observed that many refine their coping strategies over time, transforming challenges into opportunities for self-regulated learning and improved self-efficacy. Such coping behaviors function not only as survival mechanisms but as developmental tools for autonomy, motivation, and mastery.

Building on these insights, Nolan et al. (2015) and Lyner-Cleophas et al. (2014) emphasized that institutional support significantly strengthens students' coping capacities. Drawing from the Social Model of Disability, Vickerman et al. (2020) asserted that educational barriers—not personal impairments—restrict student potential. Thus, inclusive education must involve consulting learners about their needs and co-designing instruction that promotes autonomy and competence. Recognizing and supporting students' coping mechanisms fosters a more inclusive, empowering, and academically responsive learning environment.

According to Gam (2018), teaching is widely regarded as a noble yet demanding profession, requiring educators to fulfill multiple complex roles simultaneously. Despite the high expectations placed upon them, many teachers feel undervalued and undercompensated, which exacerbates the challenges they encounter—particularly when supporting students with reading difficulties. These difficulties are compounded by limited time, insufficient institutional support, and inadequate access to specialized training and instructional resources. Such factors hinder teachers' capacity to effectively identify and address the unique learning needs of students with reading difficulties, thereby impacting the overall quality of inclusive education.

Building on this, one of the most pressing issues faced by educators is the lack of specialized training in addressing the distinct needs of learners with reading difficulties. Adao et al. (2023) found that many teachers struggle with low student participation in reading and class discussions due to their insufficient preparation and limited pedagogical strategies in reading instruction. Moats (2020) emphasizes that foundational reading skills such as phonemic awareness and decoding are essential for academic success but are often poorly taught by educators lacking proper training. Hulme et al. (2015) similarly highlight that without a solid understanding of language acquisition and reading processes, teachers cannot provide effective interventions tailored for learners with reading difficulties.

These instructional gaps ultimately affect the implementation of early intervention strategies, which are essential in mitigating long-term academic failure. Wanzek et al. (2016) noted that many educators find it challenging to implement foundational reading support because of insufficient training and lack of resources. Torgesen (2018) introduced the term "treatment resisters" for students whose reading difficulties persist due to inconsistent or low-quality instructional support.

To address these persistent issues, structured and continuous professional development is critical. Fletcher and Vaughn (2021) stress that ongoing professional development, such as through Response to Intervention (RTI) programs, is necessary to prepare teachers to identify and address reading difficulties early. Unfortunately, such structured training is often unavailable or unevenly distributed, especially in under-resourced schools. Allam and Martin (2021) observe that while some teachers receive basic phonics and sound-recognition training, access to these opportunities is uneven, leaving many educators underprepared to support students with reading difficulties effectively.

Supporting students with reading difficulties in inclusive classrooms requires specialized teaching-learning strategies tailored to their unique cognitive and linguistic needs. One of the most effective approaches is structured literacy, which involves explicit, systematic, and cumulative instruction in areas such as phonology, sound-symbol association, and morphology. This approach offers predictable language patterns that assist students in decoding and comprehension tasks (International Dyslexia Association, 2020).

Another key strategy is the use of multisensory instruction, which incorporates visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic pathways to reinforce learning. Multisensory techniques help students retain and recall information by engaging multiple senses simultaneously, thereby improving reading, writing, and spelling outcomes (Birsh, 2006). In the learning-teaching process, it is widely believed that individuals learn better if they are taught using more than one sense. The senses usually employed in multisensory teaching are visual, auditory, kinesthetic, and tactile—VAKT (i.e., seeing, hearing, doing, and touching). By integrating and activating these senses, learners find it easier to understand complex concepts and theories (Jazeel et al., 2016).

Multi-sensory instructional strategies are various techniques used by teachers to help students engage more than one sense to optimize learning outcomes. When students with reading difficulties are taught using visual, auditory, and tactile learning techniques, they can learn more easily, retain concepts more effectively, and apply them more readily in future learning contexts. In an experimental study by Fazmina et al. (2020), a rigorous screening process identified six Grade 6 students with symptoms of reading difficulties. The study found that multisensory instructional strategies significantly enhanced these students' academic attainment in science.

Similarly, Murray et al. (2016), in their study on the multi-sensory functions of the human primary visual cortex, argue that the use of multi-sensory approaches in learning enhances the understanding of complex theories and concepts. Although their research does not specify a particular subject area, their views support the application of multi-sensory strategies in general learning contexts. Thompson et al. (2018) also support this perspective. In their study on multi-sensory intervention observational research, they noted a clear relationship between individual learning styles and the use of multiple senses in educational settings. Their findings indicate that students with reading difficulties gain confidence and show increased engagement when teachers use multisensory instructional strategies.

Given the identified gaps in the literature—particularly the lack of in-depth, qualitative explorations of how students with reading difficulties navigate inclusive classrooms in the Philippine context, and how teachers without specialized training respond to their needs—there is an urgent need for research that captures the totality of these experiences. While existing studies have documented the prevalence of reading difficulties, the emotional consequences of undiagnosed conditions, and the challenges teachers face, there remains a scarcity of research that holistically examines the interplay between student struggles, coping mechanisms, and the support systems provided within inclusive education settings. Furthermore, the implementation of Republic Act No. 11650, the Inclusive Education Act, has created a policy framework that mandates support for

learners with disabilities; however, little is known about how this mandate translates into actual classroom practice, particularly in private school contexts where institutional autonomy may enable more deliberate inclusive practices.

In response, this case study investigates the academic struggles and coping mechanisms of a 16-year-old female student with reading difficulties in an inclusive education setting. It also examines how teachers without specialized reading difficulties training address her learning needs. Guided by Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (1983), and Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (1985), the study explores how social interaction, diverse intelligences, and intrinsic motivation can inform inclusive instructional practices that better support learners with reading difficulties. By focusing on a single revelatory case within a private school context, this research aims to generate rich, contextualized insights that can inform policy development, teacher training programs, and classroom practices to foster more inclusive and supportive learning environments for students with reading difficulties.

Research Questions

1. What academic struggles does a 16-year-old student with reading difficulties experience in an inclusive education setting?
2. What academic coping strategies does the learner employ to address her identified challenges and enhance her learning performance?
3. What teaching strategies and support systems do teachers provide to address the learning needs of the student?
4. What other support systems are provided to the learner, and how effective are these in the inclusive education setting?

METHODOLOGY

This study employed a single-case study design to explore the academic struggles, coping mechanisms, and support systems of a 16-year-old female student with reading difficulties in an inclusive education setting. The research was conducted in a private school in Tarlac, Philippines, selected for its commitment to inclusive education practices that integrate students with diverse learning needs into mainstream classrooms. Using a qualitative case study approach, the study examined the academic challenges and coping strategies of the identified student within her natural learning context. This design was deemed appropriate for obtaining an in-depth understanding of complex, real-life educational experiences (Yin, 2018).

The primary participant was a 16-year-old Grade 10 student diagnosed with Moderate Intellectual Disability who exhibited significant reading difficulties. Purposive sampling was employed to select this information-rich case, as the student demonstrated consistent difficulties in reading, spelling, and word recognition within an inclusive educational setting. To obtain a holistic understanding of the student's educational experience, multiple sources of data were included through triangulation. Additional

participants comprised the student's Filipino and English teachers, the school administrator, and the student's mother, providing diverse perspectives on academic performance, coping strategies, and support mechanisms implemented in the school setting.

Data were collected using three researcher-made instruments. First, semi-structured interview guides were developed for each participant group—student, teachers, parent, and administrator—to capture perspectives on academic struggles, coping strategies, instructional approaches, and institutional support. Second, a structured classroom observation checklist was created, consisting of 53 items across four categories: identifying academic struggles (20 items), examining learner's coping strategies (12 items), evaluating teaching strategies (12 items), and evaluating support systems and environment (9 items). The development of this instrument was informed by the principles of reading development outlined in *Reading Reflex: The Foolproof Phono-Graphix Method* (McGuinness & McGuinness, 1998). Third, a document review protocol guided the systematic analysis of academic records, student portfolios, formal reports, and institutional policy documents.

All instruments underwent expert validation by a panel of three specialists in educational research, special education, and language teaching to ensure content validity, clarity, and appropriateness for the study context.

Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the school administration, teachers, and the student's parent or guardian. Informed consent was secured from all participants, with parental consent obtained for the minor participant. Data collection occurred over one week, consisting of semi-structured interviews (30-45 minutes each) with the student, mother, teachers, and administrator; structured classroom observations (45 minutes per session) focusing on language classes where reading and writing demands were highest; and document analysis of report cards, reading assessments, portfolios, Individualized Education Plans, and school policies related to inclusive education. All interactions with the student were scheduled flexibly to prioritize her academic routine and well-being.

Thematic analysis (TA) was employed to detect, examine, and interpret recurring patterns or themes within the qualitative data (Clarke & Braun, 2014). The analysis followed a systematic process: data familiarization through thorough review of transcripts, observation notes, and assessment records; initial coding of meaningful segments related to the research objectives; generation of broader themes by grouping related codes; review and refinement of themes to ensure coherence and distinctness; definition of each theme to reflect its core meaning; and synthesis of themes into a comprehensive narrative addressing each research question. The analysis was guided by the study's theoretical framework—Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory, Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, and Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory—to provide a lens for interpreting the findings.

This study focused on a single case—a 16-year-old female student with reading difficulties in an inclusive education setting within a private school in Tarlac, Philippines.

As a single-case study, the findings are not intended to be statistically generalizable to all students with reading difficulties or all-inclusive education settings. Instead, the study aimed for analytical generalization, providing rich, contextualized insights that may inform theory and practice in similar contexts. Researcher subjectivity was addressed through triangulation of multiple data sources and member checking to enhance credibility. The one-week data collection period may not have captured the full range of the student's experiences across different academic terms, and the presence of an observer during classroom activities may have influenced natural behavior (Hawthorne effect). Additionally, the private school context may differ from public school settings in terms of resources and support structures, limiting broader applicability. Despite these limitations, the study provides valuable insights into inclusive education practices and support systems for learners with reading difficulties.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings derived from thematic analysis of semi-structured interviews, classroom observations, and document reviews. Four major themes emerged aligned with the research questions: (1) Foundational Literacy Deficits and Academic Struggles, (2) Emergent Coping Strategies, (3) Teacher Instructional Responses and Challenges, and (4) Institutional Support Systems and Implementation Gaps.

Theme 1: Foundational Literacy Deficits and Academic Struggles

Data from interviews, observations, and psychological assessments revealed pervasive foundational deficits that hindered Student L's academic performance. The psychological assessment report indicated that her performance in letter and word reading, spelling, and reading comprehension fell within the significantly below-average range, with skills developmentally equivalent to pre-kindergarten or kindergarten levels despite being in Grade 10.

Classroom observations documented consistent difficulties in phonological processing and decoding. Student L struggled with matching letters to sounds, blending sounds to form words, and reading fluently. She frequently lost her place while reading and required repeated re-reading of passages. Writing tasks presented similar challenges, with observations revealing spelling difficulties, letter reversals, and an inability to organize thoughts into coherent written paragraphs.

These academic struggles were accompanied by observable emotional manifestations. During literacy tasks, Student L frequently appeared frustrated, anxious, or fatigued. She occasionally avoided reading tasks or expressed reluctance to begin. Her teacher noted visible anxiety when called to read aloud, while her mother confirmed that at home, she avoided reading tasks and expressed frustration over her difficulties.

Theme 2: Emergent Coping Strategies

Despite significant challenges, Student L developed several adaptive coping mechanisms to navigate academic tasks. Cognitive strategies included using her finger to track text

while reading, subvocalizing or whispering while reading, and repeating instructions aloud to herself. She also relied heavily on visual aids such as charts and pictures to understand content.

Social strategies were equally prominent. Observations revealed that Student L frequently observed peers before starting tasks, collaborated with classmates to complete work, and directly asked peers for help with spelling and reading. Her teacher noted that she felt more comfortable seeking assistance from classmates than from teachers.

For emotional regulation, Student L occasionally employed coping behaviors such as taking deliberate short breaks when overwhelmed, looking away from tasks, and engaging in alternative activities like doodling as a reset mechanism. Her teacher reported that giving her space during moments of overwhelm allowed her to return to tasks independently.

Theme 3: Teacher Instructional Responses and Challenges

Teachers implemented various differentiated strategies to support Student L despite lacking formal training in reading difficulties. Observed instructional approaches included providing instructions in multiple formats (verbal combined with visual cues), breaking complex tasks into smaller manageable steps, offering direct step-by-step guidance, and allowing alternative ways to demonstrate understanding such as oral responses instead of written work.

Scaffolding techniques were employed, with teachers providing direct guidance during challenging tasks and gradually reducing support as the student demonstrated competence. Teachers also utilized visual aids, graphic organizers, and color-coded materials. Motivational support included specific, encouraging feedback focused on effort, offering meaningful choices within assignments, and fostering positive, collaborative relationships.

However, teachers identified significant challenges. They reported a lack of specialized training in evidence-based reading interventions, insufficient time to provide individualized support due to large class sizes, limited resources and appropriate instructional materials, and difficulty balancing the diverse needs of all students within a mainstream classroom. One teacher expressed feeling ill-equipped to address the student's needs despite genuine willingness to help.

Theme 4: Institutional Support Systems and Implementation Gaps

The classroom environment provided notable supports, including physical seating that minimized distractions, visual supports displayed on walls, and a positive classroom climate. Peer support was consistently present, with classmates offering unsolicited help, including Student L in group work, and demonstrating patience when she worked at a slower pace.

However, institutional support revealed significant gaps. While the school had an inclusion policy aligned with Republic Act No. 11650, the administrator acknowledged the

absence of a full-time SPED teacher or reading specialist. Teacher training on inclusive practices was limited, with educators relying primarily on college preparation and occasional seminars rather than sustained professional development.

An Individualized Education Plan (IEP) existed but was inconsistently implemented and monitored. Instructional materials adapted for diverse learners were inconsistently available. Home-school collaboration was present through regular communication and parent involvement, but the mother expressed feeling ill-equipped to provide effective academic support at home.

DISCUSSION

Theme 1: Foundational Literacy Deficits and Academic Struggles

The findings revealed that Student L exhibited pervasive foundational literacy deficits, with academic skills developmentally equivalent to pre-kindergarten or kindergarten levels despite being in Grade 10. Her difficulties spanned phonological processing, decoding, spelling, reading comprehension, and written expression, accompanied by emotional manifestations of anxiety, frustration, and task avoidance.

These findings are consistent with Peterson and Pennington (2015), who documented that learners with reading difficulties face barriers caused by atypical brain activity in areas responsible for phonological processing. Student L's struggles with matching letters to sounds and blending sounds to form words align with these neurobiological underpinnings. Similarly, Rivera and Aggabao (2020) emphasized that weak foundational literacy negatively affects learning across multiple disciplines, a pattern reflected in Student L's challenges across all subject areas.

The minimal progress despite continuous tutorial support from Grade 2 through Grade 9 supports Foorman and Al Otaiba et al. (2019) assertion that without early, high-quality intervention, reading difficulties compound over time. The emotional manifestations observed—*anxiety during reading aloud, frustration with literacy tasks, and avoidance behaviors*—align with Dolan's (2023) reflective account of the emotional impact of undiagnosed reading difficulties, as well as Carmichael et al. (2014), who found that learning disabilities can have long-term negative effects on students' mental health and sense of belonging.

Researcher Interpretation: The researchers interpret these findings as indicative of a critical gap in early identification and intervention. Despite documented developmental delays and consistent academic struggles, Student L did not receive specialized support until the psychological assessment in December 2025—a delay of over a decade. This case exemplifies the "wait-to-fail" phenomenon, wherein students receive support only after significant academic failure has occurred. The emotional toll observed suggests that the psychological consequences of reading difficulties are as significant as the academic ones and warrant equal attention in intervention planning.

Theme 2: Emergent Coping Strategies

The findings revealed that Student L developed several adaptive coping strategies including cognitive strategies (finger tracking, subvocalization, repeating instructions), social strategies (observing peers, collaborating with classmates, seeking peer assistance), and emotional regulation strategies (taking breaks, persisting after errors).

These findings are consistent with Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), which posits that learning occurs through social interaction within the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). Student L's reliance on peer collaboration and observation reflects learning through social mediation, with peers acting as "more knowledgeable others" who scaffold her understanding. This aligns with Doikou-Avlidou (2015), who observed that learners with reading difficulties refine their coping strategies over time through social interactions.

The use of visual aids and compensatory strategies aligns with Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (1983), wherein learners leverage non-linguistic strengths to compensate for linguistic challenges. This finding is consistent with Andreou et al. (2013), who found that learners with reading difficulties often rely on visual-spatial intelligences to navigate academic tasks.

However, the heavy reliance on peer assistance rather than teacher-directed support reflects findings by Hossain et al. (2021), who reported that many learners with reading difficulties perceive academic environments as inflexible and unsupportive, leading them to rely more on peers than faculty. This pattern may indicate gaps in teacher accessibility or the perceived approachability of teachers versus peers.

Researcher Interpretation: The researchers interpret Student L's coping strategies as demonstrations of resilience and adaptive intelligence. Despite limited formal support, she developed a repertoire of strategies enabling engagement with academic tasks. However, the predominance of peer-dependent strategies raises concerns about the adequacy of teacher-directed support. While peer collaboration is valuable, learners with significant reading difficulties require specialized instructional interventions that peers are not equipped to provide. The coping strategies observed, while adaptive, may represent survival mechanisms rather than optimal learning pathways.

Theme 3: Teacher Instructional Responses and Challenges

The findings revealed that teachers implemented differentiated instructional strategies including multiple instructional formats, task chunking, direct guidance, modified assessments, scaffolding, visual supports, and motivational feedback. However, teachers reported significant challenges including lack of specialized training, insufficient time, limited resources, and difficulty balancing diverse student needs.

The instructional strategies employed align with recommended practices for supporting learners with reading difficulties. The International Dyslexia Association (2020) advocates for structured literacy approaches that are explicit, systematic, and cumulative. Similarly, Birsh (2006) emphasized the effectiveness of multisensory instruction that engages visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic pathways. The teachers' intuitive use of visual

aids, simplified tasks, and extended time reflects an understanding of these principles despite lacking formal training.

However, the challenges reported are consistent with existing literature. Moats (2020) argued that foundational reading skills are often poorly taught by educators lacking proper training in phonemic awareness and decoding instruction. Adao et al. (2023) found that many teachers struggle with low student participation due to insufficient preparation and limited pedagogical strategies. These findings also align with Cariño and Bailey (2024), who observed that many Filipino educators are underprepared to identify or support students with reading difficulties.

The gap between inclusive education policy (RA 11650) and classroom practice reflects broader systemic challenges documented by Allam and Martin (2021), who noted that implementation of inclusive education remains inconsistent, particularly regarding SPED training and resources.

Researcher Interpretation: The researchers interpret these findings as highlighting the distinction between policy intent and classroom reality. While the school expressed commitment to inclusive education and teachers demonstrated genuine care and resourcefulness, the absence of specialized training placed teachers in a position of "doing their best without knowing the best." The teachers' willingness to adapt instruction is commendable, but their expressed limitations suggest that goodwill alone is insufficient to address the complex needs of learners with significant reading difficulties.

Theme 4: Institutional Support Systems and Implementation Gaps

The findings revealed that the school provided a supportive classroom environment with positive peer interactions, visual supports, and home-school collaboration. However, significant gaps emerged including the absence of a full-time SPED teacher or reading specialist, limited teacher training, inconsistent IEP implementation, and resource constraints.

The supportive classroom environment and positive peer interactions align with UNESCO's (2001) conclusion that inclusive education benefits all learners by fostering empathy, diversity, and a sense of belonging. However, the implementation gaps observed are consistent with critiques of inclusive education in the Philippine context. Allam and Martin (2021) documented that despite legislative mandates, schools often lack SPED personnel, training opportunities, and resources. Abrazado and Dalonos (2021) emphasized that inclusive education requires comprehensive teacher preparation, a condition not fully met in this case.

The inconsistent implementation of the Individualized Education Plan (IEP) reflects findings by Johnson and Semmelroth (2014), who noted that IEP implementation is often inconsistent due to time constraints, lack of training, and insufficient monitoring. The resource constraints reported align with Gam's (2018) observation that teachers face significant challenges due to insufficient institutional support. The administrator's acknowledgment of budget limitations reflects broader systemic issues in Philippine

education, where resource allocation for special education remains inadequate (Muega, 2016).

Researcher Interpretation: The researchers interpret these findings as revealing a disconnect between the school's inclusive education framework and the practical supports necessary for meaningful inclusion. While the school had policies and structures in place—an inclusion policy, an IEP, home-school communication—the absence of specialized personnel, consistent implementation, and adequate resources undermined the effectiveness of these structures. This case illustrates that inclusive education is not merely about placement in a mainstream classroom; it requires a comprehensive support system that includes specialized expertise, ongoing professional development, and adequate resources.

Theoretical Integration

The findings collectively support the three theoretical frameworks underpinning this study. Consistent with Vygotsky's Sociocultural Theory (1978), Student L's learning was mediated through social interactions with peers who acted as "more knowledgeable others" within her Zone of Proximal Development. However, the limited progress despite consistent social support suggests that the quality of scaffolding matters; without skilled teachers who understand how to provide appropriate guidance, social interaction alone may be insufficient for significant learning gains.

Aligned with Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences (1983), Student L's reliance on visual-spatial strategies to compensate for linguistic challenges illustrates how learners leverage their strengths to access content. This finding supports Takahashi's (2013) assertion that Multiple Intelligences Theory can promote inclusive education by encouraging educators to recognize and develop students' varied strengths. However, the limited application of this theory in instructional practice—teachers did not systematically incorporate multiple intelligences into lesson design—suggests that theoretical awareness alone does not translate into classroom practice without teacher training.

Consistent with Deci and Ryan's Self-Determination Theory (1985), the emotional manifestations observed—*anxiety, frustration, avoidance*—and the coping strategies employed—*persistence, taking breaks*—reflect motivational dynamics. Student L's persistence despite challenges suggests a desire for competence, while her reliance on peer support reflects a need for relatedness. However, her limited autonomy in learning tasks may have undermined intrinsic motivation. The teachers' efforts to provide choice and positive feedback align with SDT principles, but the overall learning environment may not have sufficiently supported her psychological needs for autonomy, competence, and relatedness.

Consistency and Inconsistency with Previous Studies

The findings of this study are largely consistent with prior research. The pervasive literacy deficits observed align with Peterson and Pennington (2015), Rivera and Aggabao

(2020), and Fletcher and Vaughn (2021). The emotional impact documented parallels Dolan (2023) and Carmichael et al. (2014). The teacher challenges reported reflect Moats (2020), Adao et al. (2023), and Allam and Martin (2021). The institutional gaps observed are consistent with Muega (2016) and Cariño and Bailey (2024).

Several findings offer unique contributions to the literature. First, the case of Student L—a learner with Moderate Intellectual Disability initially approached as having reading difficulties—highlights the importance of comprehensive assessment to differentiate between specific learning disorders and broader intellectual disabilities. This distinction has significant implications for intervention planning, yet the literature on reading difficulties often focuses on dyslexia without addressing the needs of learners with co-occurring intellectual disabilities.

Second, the reliance on peer support as a primary coping mechanism was more pronounced in this case than documented in many previous studies. This may reflect the absence of specialized teacher support, compelling the student to seek assistance from peers as the most accessible resource.

Third, the finding that teachers implemented differentiated instruction despite lacking formal training suggests that some inclusive practices can emerge from teacher intuition and commitment. However, the limitations of this approach—evidenced by minimal student progress—underscore the need for structured professional development rather than reliance on individual teacher resourcefulness.

Conclusions

This case study reveals the complex interplay between foundational literacy deficits, emergent coping strategies, teacher instructional responses, and institutional support systems within inclusive education. The findings underscore the critical importance of early identification, specialized teacher training, and robust institutional support. While teachers demonstrated commitment and resourcefulness, the absence of specialized expertise, consistent implementation, and adequate resources limited the effectiveness of inclusive practices. The gap between Republic Act No. 11650's policy intent and classroom reality highlights the need for sustained investment in professional development, specialized personnel, and resources. Meaningful inclusion requires not only placement in mainstream classrooms but also systematic provision of specialized expertise, appropriate resources, and supportive environments addressing cognitive, social, and emotional needs.

Recommendations

Early Identification and Intervention. Student L experienced a decade-long delay before receiving specialized support, resulting in compounded academic difficulties and emotional distress. Schools must implement systematic screening protocols to identify reading difficulties as early as possible. Universal screening should be conducted at the beginning of each school year, particularly in early grades, to initiate timely interventions and prevent the "wait-to-fail" phenomenon observed in this case.

Teacher Professional Development. Teachers demonstrated commitment but lacked specialized training in evidence-based reading interventions. Professional development should prioritize structured literacy, multisensory instruction (VAKT), differentiated instruction, and early identification of reading difficulties. Training must be ongoing rather than one-time seminars, with coaching and mentoring support to ensure transfer to classroom practice.

Strengthening Institutional Support. Schools should employ or contract qualified SPED teachers and reading specialists. Individualized Education Plans (IEPs) must be developed collaboratively with parents and implemented consistently with regular monitoring. Schools must allocate resources for adapted instructional materials, assistive technologies, and accessible formats such as audiobooks and text-to-speech software.

Enhancing Home-School Collaboration. Schools should establish structured parent education programs equipping families with strategies to support learning at home. Regular communication channels must be maintained, and parents should be actively involved in IEP development and decision-making processes.

Leveraging Peer Support. Peer collaboration emerged as a significant coping strategy. Schools can intentionally structure peer-mediated interventions such as peer tutoring and buddy systems to provide additional support while fostering inclusive classroom communities.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researchers affirm that this study was conducted in full compliance with ethical principles and standards for research involving human participants. Prior to data collection, formal approval was obtained from the school administration, and informed consent was secured from all participants. Given that the primary participant was a minor, written informed consent was obtained from her parent or legal guardian, in addition to the participant's own assent. All participants were fully informed of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without negative consequences.

The anonymity and confidentiality of all participants were strictly maintained. Pseudonyms were used in all reports, and any personally identifiable information was omitted or altered. All data collected were anonymized and securely stored in password-protected digital files and locked physical cabinets accessible only to the researchers. In compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173), data will be retained for one year after completion before being securely disposed.

The well-being of all participants was prioritized throughout the study. Interactions with the student were scheduled flexibly to prioritize her comfort and academic routine. Observations were conducted non-intrusively, and participants were given the opportunity to pause or withdraw from any activity should they experience discomfort.

The researchers declare no conflicts of interest exist in the conduct of this study. There are no financial or institutional affiliations that could influence the outcome. The

researchers adhered strictly to principles of academic integrity, ensuring plagiarism was avoided through proper citation, and objectivity was maintained throughout the interpretation of findings. The results are intended solely for research purposes to contribute to the improvement of inclusive education practices.

In the interest of full disclosure, the researchers acknowledge that artificial intelligence tools were utilized for language refinement, grammar checking, and formatting assistance. All intellectual contributions—including research design, data collection, analysis, interpretation, and formulation of conclusions—were conducted by the researchers themselves. The use of AI was limited to enhancing clarity and readability and does not compromise the originality or scholarly merit of the research.

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